

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B441
 Date: 28(Z)-29 Apr 2009
 Take Off: 23:55:00Z
 Landing: 04:49:34Z
 Flight Time 4h 54m 34s

Campaign: MEVEX Maritime Flight 3
Operating Area: Ocean, E of Muscat

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Jon Taylor	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Jim Crawford	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
13	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
ViRC chat log	No contact with aircraft so log not included (mainly connect/disconnect msgs)
Brief	Sortie brief to be added
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
AVAPS log	AVAPS log to be completed
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	No log passed to FAAM yet
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS	No log passed to FAAM yet
Mini-Lidar	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_000244_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_005702_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_015855_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_025912_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_000231_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_005652_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_015652_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_015848_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_025903_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_035903_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_000226_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_005644_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_015644_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_015842_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_025900_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_035900_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_000238_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_005657_25hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090429_r0_b441_015735_25hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B441
 Date: 28/29 April 2009
 Project: MEVEX
 Location: maritime

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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233714		GIN	0.18 kft	266	started
234205		Start-Up	0.18 kft	268	
234537		ASP	0.18 kft	264	open
235500		T/O	11.3 kft	127	muscat
241053		transit	19.0 kft	129	fl190
242252		heimann	19.0 kft	087	cal 11
244135	250118	Profile 1	19.0 - 3.1 kft	088	
244410		bbr	16.8 kft	090	extend
244714		P1	14.1 kft	090	interrupt
244914		P1	14.3 kft	256	resumed
250145		bbr	3.1 kft	205	retract
250223		heimann	3.2 kft	119	cal 11
250248	251115	Run 1.1	3.2 - 3.1 kft	092	
250929		!	3.1 kft	091	abeam f79 miss; too close
251526	252030	Run 1.2	3.1 kft	276	
251731		!	3.1 kft	273	abeam f79 at bottom edge of box
252058		heimann	3.1 kft	205	cal 11
252239	252824	Run 1.3	3.1 kft	068	
252446		!	3.1 kft	094	abeam f79 good pass
253018	253648	Run 1.4	3.2 - 3.1 kft	267	
253347		!	3.1 kft	270	abeam f79 good pass
253731		heimann	3.1 kft	188	cal 11
253831	254424	Run 1.5	3.2 - 3.1 kft	086	
254115		!	3.1 kft	090	abeam f79 good pass
254559	255249	Run 1.6	3.2 - 3.1 kft	259	
254920		!	3.1 kft	266	abeam f79 good pass
255505	260052	Run 1.7	3.1 kft	073	
255745		!	3.1 kft	093	abeam f79 good pass
260234	260613	Run 1.8	3.2 - 3.1 kft	264	
260551		!	3.1 kft	267	abeam f79 good pass
260923		heimann	5.1 kft	281	cal 11
261124	261755	Run 2.1	5.1 kft	074	
261433		!	5.1 kft	094	abeam f79 miss; too close 5x beam from centre
261942	262624	Run 2.2	5.1 kft	282	
262306		!	5.1 kft	273	abeam f79 miss; too close 4x beam from centre
262758	263604	Run 2.3	5.1 kft	100	
263118		!	5.1 kft	096	abeam f79 miss; too far 5x beam from centre
263921	264224	Run 2.4	5.1 kft	275	
264214		!	5.1 kft	273	abeam F79 miss; too close 5x beam on centre
264748	265413	Run 3.1	10.1 kft	082	
265138		!	10.1 kft	095	abeam f79 good pass
265507		heimann	10.1 kft	358	cal 11
265627	265904	Run 3.2	10.1 kft	272	

265816		!	10.1 kft	271 abeam f79 miss; too close
265912	271712	Profile 2	10.1 - 0.17 kft	271 1012 qnh
270600		!	4.2 kft	270 rod >500ft min
271150		P2	1.1 kft	270 interrupt
271336		P2	1.0 kft	093 resume
271712	273246	Run 4.1	0.17 - 0.24 kft	083 1012 qnh
271753		heimann	0.23 kft	089 cal 11
273003		!	0.16 kft	097 abeam f79
273605	274231	Run 5.1	3.1 kft	273
273949		!	3.0 kft	269 abeam f79 good pass
274312		heimann	3.1 kft	198 cal 11
274520	274719	Run 5.2	3.1 kft	088
274643		!	3.1 kft	087 abeam f79 miss; too close
274934	275130	Run 5.3	3.1 kft	294
275115		!	3.1 kft	273 abeam f79 miss; too close
275630	281908	Profile 3	0.14 - 24.0 kft	279
281937		transit	24.0 kft	282
284934		Land	0.11 kft	177 Muscat 04:49:34
285241		pirouette 1	0.11 kft	126 125M start
285507		pirouette 1	0.11 kft	127 end
285739		ASP	0.11 kft	086 closed

B441 21:42:31-29:08:13

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

Mission Scientist's Log

MEVEX MARITIME ~~SUNRISE~~ FLIGHT

28/29 JAN 09

Flight No **B.441** Date Name SON TANNER Page 1 of 7

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
240307					TAKE OFF DEUSLAT
					PASP $\approx$ 1800/cc at f10
					4000/cc peak
					3500/cc at 5000ft
					Neph slows. $\approx$ 200m ⁻¹ at
					5000ft = 100m ⁻¹ then increases again
					to 180m ⁻¹ at 7500ft then falls
					down to 0 at 16500ft.
240810		16700 m (1013)			6m s' / 1196 deg T = -3.39
			128 deg		Td = -23.68
					Below 8000ft wind $\approx$ 250 to 300°
					slow wind 150 to 250 1000ft
					15000ft
241050		F190	129	23° 6' N 59° 18' E	wind 005 / 25k deg
					T = -8.37 / -32.6
243008					F79 22° 58' 082E North 9kts.
					QNT 1008 kPa.
243410		F190	087	22° 56' N 61° 18' E	As sky lightens can see stars
					in significant higher level Ci
					would today. $\approx$ 5 to 6/8 Ci?
					Ship turned onto 090 deg
					persistent contrails

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B. 649** Date **28/29 AM** Name **Jon Tarnal** Page **2** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
24394					Water shows significant changes in aerox as we head east on track. surface haze developing notably. Htz upper haze increasing and becoming more intense Htz lower haze decreasing
24435	PI ↓	FL190 FL163			start of PI ↓ to ~3000ft Htz aerox low. scattering ↑
244710	PI	FL160	090	22°56'N 62°30'E	Interrupt PI East of ship.
244914	PI ↓	FL160	255	23°N 62°40'E	Restart PI
					Cycle on 35 → 20m ⁻¹ R=O=R.
250118	PI	3000ft			End of PI
250123					F7 2258N 062 05'E Htz 090.
250248	PI-1	3000ft	093	2256°N 61°38'E	Start PI-1 towards ship [REDACTED] wind 006 / 255 T=38.23 [REDACTED] Td = 7.01%
					Clouds present
250924					A clear ship - slightly too close no IRG imagery but on spots. Water shows aerox tops at 700m below. looks like 6/8 Ci persistent central
251115	PI-1	3000ft	093	22°56'N 62°12'E	end of PI-1

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.44**..... Date **28/29 APR** Name **Jon TARNON** Page **3** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
251526	1.2	3000ft	276	22°56'N 62°12'E	Start Run 1.2 observed solar azim sol zen = 91.28°
251731	1.2	3000ft	276		A beam ship 1RL saw deck ✓✓ and awashhale Aerial down at western end of
252036	1.2	3000ft			run 1.2 End
252239	1.3	3000ft	080	22°56'N 62°E	Run 1.3 Start observed
252446		3000ft		22°56'N 62°12'E	A beam ship 1RL ✓✓ 006 / 268° T = 29.76 Td = -1.75°C observed
252824	R1.3	3000ft			End R1.3
253018	R1.4	3000ft	270	22°56'N 62°18'E	St R1.4 011 / 279° T = 29.58 Td = -1.71°C observed
253347	R1.4	3000ft	270	22°56'N 62°6'E	a beam ship 1RL ✓✓ ditch stars used by close to square further west way.
253648	R1.4	3000ft		23°N 61°56'E	End R1.4

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.441**... Date **28/29 APR** Name **Jon Taylor** Page **4** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
25383	1.5	3000ft	083	22°56'N 62°0'E	St Run 1.5 ship 12nm ahead 005/267 deg. ship hdg 090.
					XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
254115	1.5	3000ft			Abeam ship 1RC VVV Good wake capture also. $\theta = 85.32^\circ$
254626		3000ft		22°56'N 62°26'E	End Run 1.5
254559	1.6	3000ft	256°	22°56'N 62°26'E	St Run 1.6 ship 16nm off wind 011/280°. $T = 29.57$ $Td = -1.58$
254920	1.8	3000ft		22°56'N 62°12'E	Abeam ship 1RC VVV. XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
252249	1.8	3000ft		22°56'N 61°56'E	End Run 1.6 $T = 30.32$ 007/253°. $Td = -1.96$ 8/8 clear above.
255518	1.7	3000ft	070	22°56'N 62°0'E	St Run 1.7 ship 12nm ahead XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX $\theta = 82^\circ$
255745	1.7	3000ft	090	22°56'N 62°12'E	Abeam ship 1RC = VVV Good stern wake
260052	1.7	3000ft		22°56'N 62°30'E	End 1.7 wind 007/278 deg. $T = 29.55$ $Td = -1.92^\circ$

Mission Scientist's Log

10 5000ft
5 4000ft
20 10000ft
20 4000ft above
Run 15 15. 3000ft 4000ft
20 20 85

Flight No **B.441** Date **28/29 APR** Name **SON TAEWON** Page **5** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
260234	1.8	3000ft	262	22°58'N 62°24'E	St Run 1.8 13nm away
260551			290		Abeam ship 1RC = VV XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
					still 8/8 Ci above but thin $\theta = 80.77^\circ$
260613	1.8	3000ft		22°57'N 62°12'E	End Run 1.8 + climb to 5000ft
261124	2.1	5000ft			st Run 2.1 alt 1000. Ship 13nm ahead. XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
261633		5000ft	090		Abeam ship 1RC = NO. In vessel lower
261755	2.1	5000ft			End Run 2.1
261962	2.2	5000ft	281	22°55'N 62°30'E	st Run 2.2 ship 1km wind 007 / 287kts $T = 24.38$ $Td = -6.38^\circ C$ XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
262306		5000ft	273	22°56'N 62°18'E	Abeam ship 1RC = NO.
262624	2.2	5000ft		22°56' 62°00'E	End Run 2.2
262758	2.3	5000ft	096	22°56'N 62°06'E	st Run 2.3 ship 1km ahead. XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
263118					Abeam ship 1RC = NO. $\theta = 75^\circ$
263604	2.3	5000ft			End Run 2.3 22°57.5'N 062°22.6'E 090 10kts

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B44** Date **28/29 Apr** Name **Jon Towner** Page **6** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
263921	R2.4	5000ft	275	22°56'N 62°30'E	St Run 2.4 ship 13m ahead. clouds at 1000ft
264216					Abeam ship IRC = NO
264224	R2.4	5000ft			End Run 2.4 + climb to 10000ft still in abeam
264968	R3.1	10000ft	075	22°56'N 62°46'E	St Run 3.1 P ₀ = 1009. ship 5m at top of ascent lev clouds at 1000ft
265138	R3.1	10000ft	098	22°56'N 62°26'E	Abeam ship IRC = ✓✓
265413	R3.1	10000ft		22°56'N 62°36'E	End Run 3.1
265627	R3.2	10000ft	290		St Run 3.2 clouds at 1000ft
265816					Abeam ship IRC = wind 000/018deg T = 11.66 Td = -21.13°C
2659 ⁰⁰ 265912	R3.2 P2↓	10000ft↓	271	23N 26.4E	End Run 3.2 + start of PH
270854					PLASP ca 650/cc 2500ft.
271150	P2	10000ft		22°56'N 61°26'E	Interrupt Profile 1013ms
271336.	P2↓	10000ft↓	092		Restart Profile ↓
271712	P2	1000ft	090	22°56'N 61°42'E	End Run P2 @ 1000ft
"	R4.1	1000ft			Start Run 4.1 clouds at 1000ft Passed ship. wind 005/198°. clouds at 1000ft
273001		1000ft			Passed abeam ship

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B444** Date **28/29 APR** Name **Jon Taylor** Page **7** of **7**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
273246	R4.1	1000ft	090		End Run 4.1 + climb to 3000ft SST $\approx 27.1^{\circ}\text{C} + 0.5^{\circ}$
273605	R5.1	3000ft	272	22° 56' N 62° 42' E	St Run 5.1 ship 15nm wind 009 / 286deg. T = 29.73 Td = -1.45. XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
273809	R5.1	3000ft			Abeam ship IRC = $\checkmark\checkmark$
274231	R5.1	3000ft		22° 56' N 62° 18' E	End Run 5.1
274520	R5.2	3000ft	090	22° 55' N 62° 24' E	St Run 5.2 heading back towards ship. wind 5 / 274° T = 30.48 Td = -2.52 XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
274643					Abeam ship IRC = NO.
274719	5.2	3000ft	090	22° 52' N 62° 36' E	End Run 5.2
274934	5.3	3000ft	275		St Run 5.3 XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX
275115		3000ft			Abeam ship IRC = NO
275130	5.3				End Run 5.3 descend to 1000ft and then profile out on way home
275630	P3	1000ft ⁹¹	285		St P3 1000ft $\uparrow$ Body log master Minits do not slow square ducts still 7/8 dia
281908	P3	FL260		23° 18' N 60° 30' E	End P3 In transit home Promote at end.

IIR CAMERA
'HITS'

No. 2

Aircraft Scientist's Log

17. = 50%

8₂/₁₁ 3000' Flight No **B441** Date **29-4-09** Name **DEK** Page **1** of **4**

0/4 3000'
1/2 10000'

IIR
CAMERA
'HITS'

1. X

2. 1/2

3. ✓

4. ✓

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
234530			→		OFF CHOCS, BAY 24, MUSCAT.
2355			→		T/O MUSCAT & climb to transit alt.
					Temp inversion top ~970 mbs (~1200'). D Pt dropped ~5°C too surface to this level.
					Small 'lid' to BL top at 5000-4500'.
					Another 'lid' to BL top at 12000'.
001100					NEW LEVEL AT FL190 TRANSIT ALT.
004135	P1 &	FL190	093°	230.0N 6200 E.	START P1 7/8 Ci cover above & to E. (+ persistent contrails)
0058					Significant layer 9500'. (dries above rapidly & slt inversion).
010248	START 1.1	3000'	093°		Start 1 st retrack. Wind:
0105			→		WIND 250-255°/10-12kt.
010929		Abeam now.			Too close for IIR Field of View
011115	END 21.1	3000'			Wind 260°/15kt. Many contrails present.
011526	START 21.2	3000'	275°	2° 34' N 62° 12' E	Wind 280°/20kt
011731		Abeam			Friction too close, but got ^{SHIP} TOP OF SHIP in view
012030	END 21.2	3000'			
0122		SURPRISE LOCALLY HIGH			
012239	START 21.3	3000' (3.1kft)	078°		Adjusting hdg to align just to port of A/C.
012446		Abeam now.			GOOD PASS - Centre of IIR Camera
012824	END 21.3	3000'			
013018	START 21.4	3000'	270°		
013347		Abeam now.			GOOD PASS - Centre of IIR Camera.
013648	END 21.4	3000' (3.1kft)			

[2600 = 0200 #]

Aircraft Scientist's Log No. 2

Flight No **B44** Date **29-4-09** Name **JRK** Page **2** of **4**

	GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	013831	START R1.5	3000 FT.	083°		
5. ✓	014115		Abeam now.			Good Pass - Centre of screen on IIR Cam. [3-4 ship lengths of wake]
	014424	END R1.5				
	014559	START R1.6	3,000 FT (3.1 kft)	265°		WIND 280°/20KT.
6. ✓	014920		Abeam now	→		Good Pass Again
	015249	END R1.6	3000 FT.	281°		IIR Camera must be ahead of 285/Horace
						Will perform further racetrack at 3000 ft (2 passes)
	015505	START R1.7	3000 FT	084°	22° 34' N 62° 00' E	
7. ✓	5745.	←	Abeam now			Good capture on IIR Camera (TIMELY IIR Cam - 2 SEC FROM HORACE)
	020052	END R1.7				
	020234	START R1.8	3000 FT	270°		285°/20KT.
8. ✓	020551		Abeam now.			
	020613	END R1.8				Press 'double barrel' switched off to recover on this run.
			Climb to 5000'			
	021124	START R2.1	5000 FT (5.1 kft)	085°	25° 54' N 65° 06' E	Start 1st racetrack at this level.
9. X	021433		Abeam now.			NOTHING SEEN - TOO CLOSE TO TARGET
	021755	END R2.1				
	021942	START R2.2	5000 FT	281°		Leg 2, Racetrack 1 at 5000 FT
10. X	022306		Abeam now			Still Too Close, NOTHING SEEN on IIR
	022624	END R2.2	5000 FT.			
	022758	START R2.3	5000 FT	093°		Leg 1, Racetrack 2 at 5000 FT.
11. X			Abeam now			Too Far AWAY, NOTHING SEEN on IIR.
	023921.	END R2.3	5000 FT	275°		
12. X	024214		Abeam now			Too Close, NOTHING SEEN.
	024224	END R2.4	5000 FT			END 5000' Racetracks; Climb to FL100

0247 New D, INT & HGT values & EXPD AT END OF THIS XROW (just below 10,000 FT) } DET
LARGE
ABOVE

Aircraft Scientist's Log No. 2

Flight No **B-44** | Date **29-4-09** Name **DK** Page **3** of **4**

	GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	024748	START R3-1	FL100 (10.1kft)	078°		Start Racetrack at 10,000 FT.
13 ✓	025138		Abeam	now		GOOD CAPTURE w/ IR Cam. (Middle of beam)
	025413	END R3-1				
	0255					123° / 2kt.
	025627	START R3-2	FL100	272°		Start 2 nd leg, racetrack @ this level
14 x	0257		Abeam			NIL WIND (CALM).
	025859	END R3-2	10.1kft			SLIGHTLY LOW on COM (Too close);
	025912	START P2	From 10,000' ↓ 1000', then 1000' at 1000' / min			
	030530		Slow DESCENT RATE → 500' / min from ~ +2kft.			
	031150	Interrupt P2	1000'			Turning in Profile ↷.
	031336	Resume P2	1000' ↓			
			Approx 500' - 1000' }			V. sharp change in D.P.T 0° → +20°C
		Conditions for GOOD SURFACE DUCT?				Inversion +28°C → +33°C
	031712	END P2 / START R4.	1000'	090°	22° 54' N 61° 48' E	END P2 / Start R4
	033000		Passing ship. at 1000' now (to port).			
	033246	END R4	1000' (0.2kft)			END R4. (Climb to 3000' for (extra) final racetrack pattern. & IR Camera action.
	033605	START R5-1	3000' (3.0kft)	277°		leg 1 of Racetrack at 3000'
15 ✓	033949		Abeam SHIP.			GOOD PASS.
	034231	END R5-1				
	034520	START R5-2	3000'	089°		leg 2 of Racetrack at this level.
	034530				Wind	277° / 10kft. Temp +30°C DPT -1°C
16 x	034643	END R5-2	Abeam SHIP.			Missed and capture ^{IR}
	034719	END R5-2				END leg 2. Will turn ↷ & make 1 final approach at 3000'.

Cloud Physics Flight Log B441

Date: 28/04/09	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 21:54:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?												No
Pre-flight checks	Vref	7.5	Ref V (~3):	2.89	Vref (>7):	unknown	El#1 V (>1):	-2.5	Ref V:	3.3V	Comms?	
	Sample flow	1.35			Flow (~1):	0.68	El#32 V (>1):	-2.3				
	Sheath flow	16.99			Pressure:	1006						
					Temp (NDIT)	32.7						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
00:02:00													Heaters on
00:41:33	FL190			40	0.1	20	0.06				19		Start Profile 1
00:42:45	FL180			50	0.1	30	0.06				20		Old PCASP ch1 noisy
00:43:51	FL170			50	0.2	45	0.06						
00:44:55	FL160			60	0.2	65	0.08						
00:46:01	FL150			100	0.2	75	0.08						
00:47:13	FL140	0.1	4	100	1.5	95	0.11						
00:50:47	FL130	0.1	4	100	1.5	85	0.11						
00:51:45	FL120	0.1	4	100	1.5	95	0.11						
00:52:39	FL110	0.1	4	100	1.5	90	0.10						
00:53:27	FL100	0.1	4	200	1.5	200	0.09						
00:54:30	FL090	0.2	8	350	1.5	400	0.09						
00:55:41	FL080	0.2	7	400	1.5	500	0.09				21		
00:56:49	FL070	0.2	7	450	1.5	540	0.09						
00:57:57	FL060	0.2	7	300	1.5	500	0.09						Heaters off
00:59:15	FL050	0.2	7	500	1.5	630	0.09						
01:00:15	FL040	0.3	7	600	1.5	690	0.09						
01:01:23	FL030	0.25	10	500	1.5	610	0.09				22		End of Profile
01:02:48	3000'												Start Run 1.1
01:03:00		0.2	7	550	1.5	600	0.09				24		
01:05:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	560	0.09				25		
01:07:00		0.2	7	550	1.5	560	0.09						
01:09:00		0.25	7	550	1.5	590	0.09						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
01:11:15													End of Run
01:15:26	3000'												Start Run 1.2
01:16:00		0.2	7	575	1.5	580	0.09				28		
01:18:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	570	0.09				30		
01:20:00		0.3	7	575	1.5	540	0.09						
01:20:29													End of Run
01:22:38	3000'												Start Run 1.3
01:23:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	570	0.09						
01:25:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	560	0.09				31		
01:27:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	570	0.09				32		
01:28:24													End of Run
01:30:18	3000'												Start Run 1.4
01:31:00		0.3	7	580	1.5	570	0.09				33		
01:33:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	550	0.09				34		
01:35:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	550	0.09						
01:36:50													End of Run
01:38:32	3000'												Start Run 1.5
01:39:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	530	0.09				35		
01:41:00		0.25	7	550	1.5	550	0.09				36		
01:43:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	560	0.09				37		
01:44:25													End of Run
01:46:00	3000'												Start Run 1.6
01:47:00		0.3	10	550	1.5	545	0.09				38		
01:49:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	545	0.09						
01:51:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	530	0.09				39		
01:52:50													End of Run
01:54:53	3000'												Start Run 1.7
01:55:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	530	0.09				40		
01:57:00		0.3	7	550	1.5	530	0.09				41		
01:59:00		0.3	10	550	1.5	570	0.09				42		
02:00:53													End of Run
02:02:35													Start Run 1.8
02:03:00		0.3	10	550	1.5	540	0.09				43		
02:05:00		0.3	10	550	1.5	530	0.09						
02:06:15													End of Run
02:11:25	5000'												Start Run 2.1

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
02:12:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	430	0.09				45		
02:14:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	440	0.09						
02:16:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	430	0.09				46		
02:17:55													End of Run
02:19:41													Start Run 2.2
02:20:00	5000'	0.2	7	500	1.5	480	0.08						
02:22:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	455	0.09				47		
02:24:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	430	0.09						
02:26:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	430	0.09						
02:26:23													End of Run
02:28:00	5000'												Start Run 2.3
02:29:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	400	0.09				48		
02:31:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	430	0.08						
02:33:00		0.15	7	500	1.5	445	0.09						
02:35:00		0.15	7	500	1.5	425	0.09				49		
02:36:07													End of Run
02:39:12	5000'												Start Run 2.4
02:40:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	520	0.09				50		
02:42:00		0.15	7	500	1.5	430	0.09						
02:42:28													End of Run
02:47:49	10000'												Start Run 3.1
02:48:00		0.1	7	180	1	110	0.09				51		
02:50:00		0.1	7	180	1	110	0.09						
02:52:00		0.1	4	150	1	130	0.09						Old PCASP heater on
02:54:14													End of Run
02:56:29	10000'												Start Run 3.2
02:57:00		0.1	4	160	1	120	0.09						
02:59:05	FL100	0.1	4	150	1	110	0.09				52		End of Run & Start Profile 2
03:00:55	FL090	0.2	6	450	1.5	410	0.09						
03:02:00	FL080	0.2	6	500	1.5	510	0.09						
03:03:04	FL070	0.2	6	500	1.5	540	0.09						
03:03:53	FL060	0.2	7	500	1.5	500	0.09						
03:04:58	FL050	0.2	7	500	1.5	510	0.08						
03:06:24	FL040	0.2	7	550	1.5	600	0.09						Heater off on Old PCASP
03:08:16	FL030	0.2	7	500	2	630	0.09						
03:10:01	FL020	0.2	7	500	2	640	0.09						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
03:11:50	FL010	0.5	5	450	2	600	0.1				55		
03:17:10	100'												End of Profile 2 & Start Run 4
03:18:00		0.5	7	450	1.5	560	0.09				61		
03:20:00		0.5	7	450	1.5	600	0.09				62		
03:22:00		0.6	7	450	1.5	650	0.09				63		
03:24:00		0.6	7	450	1.5	660	0.09				64		
03:26:00		0.6	7	450	1.5	640	0.09				65		
03:28:00		0.5	7	450	1.5	580	0.09				66		
03:30:00		0.6	7	450	1.5	630	0.09				67		
03:32:00		0.5	7	450	1.5	600	0.09						
03:32:47													End of Run
03:36:05	3000'												Start Run 5.1
03:37:00		0.3	7	500	1.5	550	0.09				69		
03:39:00		0.3	7	450	1.5	550	0.09						
03:41:00		0.3	7	450	1.5	540	0.09				70		
03:42:35													End of Run
03:44:19	3000'												Start Run 5.2
03:45:00		0.3	7	500	1.5	490	0.09				71		
03:47:00		0.3	7	500	1.5	530	0.09				72		
03:47:30													End of Run
03:49:37	3000'												Start Run 5.3
03:50:00		0.3	7	475	1.5	520	0.09				73		
03:51:34	3000'												End of Run & Start P2
03:52:51	FL020	0.3	7	500	1.5	680	0.10				74		
03:54:15	FL010	0.3	7	450	1.5	575	0.09						
03:56:30	100'	0.5	7	430	1.5	600	0.09				75		End of Profile & Start P3
03:57:40	FL010	0.4	7	400	1.5	500	0.10				76		
03:58:37	FL020	0.4	7	400	1.5	430	0.10						
03:59:30	FL030	0.4	7	400	1.5	430	0.10						
04:00:32	FL040	0.3	7	400	1.5	420	0.09				77		
04:01:39	FL050	0.2	5	400	1.5	330	0.09						
04:02:47	FL060	0.2	5	400	1.5	310	0.09						
04:03:35	FL070	0.2	5	400	1.5	300	0.10						
04:04:32	FL080	0.2	5	350	1.5	240	0.10						
04:05:23	FL090	0.2	5	350	1.5	225	0.10				78		
04:06:07	FL100	0.2	5	300	1.5	230	0.09						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
04:07:05	FL110	0.2	5	200	1.5	100	0.09						Heaters on
04:07:55	FL120	0.1	5	100	1	40	0.12						
04:08:47	FL130	0.1	3	100	1.5	40	0.12						
04:09:30	FL140	0.1	3	100	1.5	40	0.13						
04:10:18	FL150	0.1	5	100	1.5	35	0.15						
04:11:11	FL160	0.1	5	100	1.5	35	0.11						
04:12:17	FL170			30	0.5	15	0.08						
04:13:17	FL180			30	0.5	10	0.07						
04:14:22	FL190			30	0.3	10	0.06						
04:15:15	FL200			20	0.3	10	0.06						CH1 noise on old PCASP just starting
04:16:15	FL210			20	0.3	5	0.07						
04:17:24	FL220			15	0.2	5	0.06						
04:18:10	FL230			15	0.2	3	0.06						
04:19:06	FL240			15	0.2	5	0.06						End of Profile 3
04:35:35													Heaters off except old PCASP
04:41:13													Old PCASP heater off

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	unknown	Noisy Ch1 when high and cold
	Flow:	0.72	
2DC	El#1:	-1.5	
	El#32:	-1.5	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.64	Noisy
	Flow:	1.14	
CDP	Laser V:	4.10	Higher laser volts when cooler
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.6	
SID 3	Laser V:	N/a	
Rack Equipment		1.2GB	Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B441

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problem

OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B441

Date: 28/29 April 2009

Instruments

cloud physics

SID3 not operated

old pcasp works ok below fl180, noisy above, channel 2 & higher ok

new pcasp noise from SWS 28V ? data not recorded after short start recording

CVI – ok

IIR – good

wet neph ok

dry neph ok

Nevezorov; failed sensor, not operated

Chemistry – good data

AVAPS – no sondes

MARSS – good data

SWS/SHIMS -lower shims not operated

ARIES – good data

Mini Lidar – good data

filters – not flown

FWVS – good data

SATCOM-H: mpds service good

GIN – serviceable

AMTG screen blanked although unit still operated

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

B441

2x beams low or edge 5x B or centre
 1x B " 4x B "
 2x B high or edge 5x B or centre
 2x B low " 5x B "

Pre-Flighter's Log

^ Clipboard power button

Date: 29/04/09

Flight No: B441

Pre-Flighter: PHIL ROSENBERG

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	CHEMISTRY OPERATOR
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☐	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	☐	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
8	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	NOT RUN
12	☒	GPS	Checked	
13	☒	INU	Align	N/A
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	INSIDE OF BW PRISM GLASS CLEANED.
15	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	CHEM OPERATOR
16	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	CHEM OPERATOR
17	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	
18	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	N/A
19	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
20	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	☒	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	☒	GE	Balance checked	
23	☒	INU	Navigate then back to Align	N/A

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	CNC	Butanol filled	NOT FUNCTIONING
25	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	NEPH OPERATOR
26	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
27	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	N/A
28	☐			
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☒	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
42	☒	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
43	☒	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed
45	☒	ICEX applied		
46	☒	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more
47	☒	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

ARIES flight log

Flight: B441 page 7 of 2

Date: 28/04/09 Operator(s): S. ROGERS Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEVEX: Ship wake

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
-21:35	—						Power On OK
-11:55	TAKE OFF						local time: silly o'clock
11 59 27	↑	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal macro.
00 11 00	FL190	Nadir	NZ	0	81	41	Nadir Zeith 30 sec macro ↳ Str 00 41
01 02 50	^{R1.1} 3000'	N3min	N	0	80	41	Nadir 3min ^{01.11} A bit murky outside.
01 15 30	^{R1.2}	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir 3min end 01 21 ↗ ops - should have been Z
01 22 -	^{R1.3} 3000'	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir 3min
01 29 29		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
01 30 45	^{R1.4} 3000'	Z3min	Z	0	81	43	Zeith 3min
01 38 35	^{R1.5}	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir 3min
01 46 05	^{R1.6} 3000'	Z3min	Z	0	81	42	Zeith 3min Lots of CI
01 54 48	^{R1.7}	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir 3min
02 02 40	^{R1.8} 3000'	Z3min	Z	0	81	43	Zeith 3min Window 37c Mirror 36c
02 06 24	↑	cal	CH	0	81	43	CH cal.
02 11 27	^{R2.1} 5000'	N3min	N	0	81	42	Nadir 3min
02 19 45	^{R2.2}	Z3min	Z	0	81	41	Zeith 3min.
02 28 00	^{R2.3} 5000'	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min
02 39 10	^{R2.4}	Z3min	Z	0	81	41	Zeith 3min
02 42 35	↑	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
02 47 52	^{R3.1} FL100	N3min	N	0	81	41	Nadir 3min Window 35c Mirror 22c
02 56 34	^{R3.2}	Z3min	Z	0	81	41	Zeith 3min CI
02 59 20	↓	cal	CH	0	80	40	CH cal.
03 13 40	↓ 100'	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal. Z N
03 15 50	↓ 100'	240x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
03 17 30	100'	240x1	Z	0	81	41	Zeith
03 18 35	100'	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
03 20 01	"	480x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
03 23 15	"	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
03 24 30	"	480x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir Window 36c Mirror 34c
03 29	"	480x1	N	0			Nadir abeam

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	28/04/09	Flight	B441	log pages
Operator(s)	J.Bowles	Campaign	MEVEX			
Departure	Muscat	Arrival	Muscat			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on			at time	22:10		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	32°C	Ch	32°C	Ch18	31°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time	22:12		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	303	Cold	303		
Target heating						Y
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	22:17 for 2min		
Scan indication		Monitor	•	Visual	•	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual		
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} - t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	23:43:30		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.5	Cold	303.39	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	42	31	40	43	39	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again				at time		

